

CONDENSATION OF ALDEHYDES WITH AMIDES, PART XIII. OF DIHYDROCINNAMALDEHYDE

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Condensation of dihydrocinnamaldehyde with some amides has been described. Formamide does not appear to condense at all; the others give a *bisamide* product. The presence of pyridine is not helpful; occasionally it gives resin and diminishes the yield. The yields are a little smaller than those obtained from cinnamaldehyde, the highest here did not exceed 42%.

In the present paper are studied the condensations of dihydrocinnamaldehyde with a few amides. These present some contrasts with those obtained from cinnamaldehyde. The products in both the cases are the *bisamides*, which resemble very greatly the other *bisamides* already obtained in this laboratory from other aldehydes. The yields in the present case do not exceed 40%, whereas the highest yields obtained in the cinnamaldehyde-amide condensations are generally higher, the highest reaching 56%.

The influence of a trace of piperidine, which usually favours the cinnamaldehyde-amide condensation (Mehra and Pandya, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1938, 7A, 376), has been found to reduce the yield in the dihydrocinnamaldehyde-amide condensations (*vide* experimental). Temperatures higher than that of water-bath appeared favourable in both.

As in the case of several other aldehydes examined, formamide does not seem to condense at all with dihydrocinnamaldehyde under all the conditions tried, and with certain difficulty with cinnamaldehyde giving as a product what looks like a polymer (*unpublished work* by Mehra and Krishna Kumar Baslas). Table II at the end will make the comparison and the contrast clear.

EXPERIMENTAL

Condensation with Acetamide.—(i). Dihydrocinnamaldehyde (1.34 g.) and acetamide (1.18 g.) (1 : 2 mol.) were heated in a flask (air-condenser) on a water-bath (98-99°) for 6 hours. After 2 hours the reactants changed into a reddish yellow solution. The flask was cooled overnight; the contents had turned into a brownish white solid next morning. The flask was again heated for 3 hours more; on cooling, the contents solidified again. They were washed repeatedly with water first and then with ether, till milk-white needle-shaped crystals were left behind

melting at 193°. On repeated recrystallisations (alcohol and water), the melting point rose to 206-207°.

(ii). The experiment was repeated with a little pyridine (1 : 1 : 0.15 mol.), the heating being carried on for 11 hours. The same product in a slightly smaller amount was obtained (yield, Table I). (The mixed melting point was 207°).

(iii). Instead of a water-bath, an oil-bath (120-125°) was used without any pyridine. The same product in a somewhat greater yield (more than double) came out (Table I).

The condensation product is insoluble in water, ether, benzene, acetone, chloroform; soluble in hot alcohol from which it is precipitated by addition of water. The pure product does not decolourise bromine or Baeyer's reagent in the cold, suggesting absence of unsaturation. Also it gave no colour with concentrated sulphuric acid. (The crude product, however, gave all the three tests, suggesting presence of a small amount of the mono-product which was unsaturated.) [Found: N, 12.38. $C_{13}H_{13}O_2N_2$ (dihydrocinnamylidene-*bis*acetamide) requires N, 11.98 per cent: the mono-amide requires N, 8.4 per cent]. On this basis the yields in the three experiments were 10.2%, 9.35% and 25.5% respectively.

Condensation with Benzamide.—(i). The aldehyde (1.34 g.) and benzamide (2.42 g.) in 1 : 2 mol. were heated in the same way on a water-bath. The mixture became a homogeneous liquid after 1 hour, and began to solidify after 2 hours; the total heating was for 8 hours. The product was taken out as before; it was fairly pure, as in the crude state it melted at 128°, but on recrystallisation m.p. rose up to 190° and was identical with benzamide itself.

(ii). When heated with 0.15 mol. of pyridine in the same way, the same result (unchanged benzamide) was obtained.

(iii). The aldehyde and the amide were heated alone at 140-150° (*cf.* Mehra and Pandya, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1939, 9A, 508). The mixture became a homogeneous liquid in a few minutes, but they soon solidified again. The heating was continued for 2½ hours. Next morning the hard mass was taken out, crushed and washed with hot water, filtered and washed with ether. The crude product, m.p. 230°, on recrystallisation from hot alcohol melted at 244-45° (m.p. 244-45°, Mehra and Pandya, *loc. cit.*). The yield was 1.41 g.

Its solubility was less than that of the *bis*acetamide, as it was soluble only in hot alcohol or hot acetone. Its other properties are the same as already described, except that it gave a pinkish colour with concentrated sulphuric acid. [Found: N, 8.3. $C_{23}H_{22}O_2N_2$ (dihydrocinnamylidene-*bis*benzamide) requires N, 7.82 per cent].

Condensation with Propionamide.—(i). Dihydrocinnamaldehyde (1.34 g.) and propionamide (1.44 g.) were heated on a water-bath as usual; after 1½ hours a dark, brown coloured solution was formed. Even after 6 hours' heating the contents did not solidify. On cooling and keeping it overnight,

the contents became a black-brown semi-solid. After two more hours' heating and cooling, the reacting mass solidified. The usual treatment gave a white mass melting (crude) at 188°. After several recrystallisations (dilute alcohol), the m.p. became constant at 198-99°, yield 0.3 g. (or 11.6% of theory).

(ii). Heated with a trace of pyridine as before for 11 hours even, the mass was found to become solid only after cooling. The same product was obtained in a slightly smaller yield, 0.25 g. (9.6%).

(iii). The aldehyde and the amide were heated alone at 115-120° for 8 hours. The same product came out, the yield 0.75 g. (29% of theory).

(iv). A higher temperature (125-130°) did not increase the yield, but yielded a resinous mass from which only 0.32 g. could be recovered. Thus 115-120° was found the optimum temperature.

The solubilities and reactions with bromine water and Baeyer's reagent were as before. A yellow colour was obtained with concentrated sulphuric acid. [Found: N, 11.1. $C_{15}H_{22}O_2N_2$ (dihydrocinnamylidene-*bi*-propionamide) requires N, 10.64 per cent].

Condensation with n-Butyramide.—The two were heated in molecular proportions (1 : 2) on a water-bath for 7 hours, cooled and kept overnight, when a brownish yellow solid was obtained. As some of the amide had volatilised away into the neck of the flask, it was washed in with a little of absolute alcohol and the flask was heated for another 6 hours (13 hours in all). A solid was found the next morning from which a white crystalline mass, m.p. 140-41°, was extracted by the usual method. Recrystallisations (dilute alcohol) raised the melting point to 168-69°. The yield was 0.32 g. (21.5% of theory).

It is soluble in dilute hot alcohol, and hot benzene; it does not react with bromine water, Baeyer's reagent or strong sulphuric acid. (Found N, 9.22. Dihydrocinnamylidene-*bis*-*n*-butyramide, $C_{17}H_{26}O_4N_2$ requires N, 9.65 per cent).

Condensation with n-Heptamide.—(i). Heating the two alone on a water-bath, solidification was found to start in 4 hours. The total heating was for 7 hours; the crude product extracted therefrom melted at 125°. To a hot alcoholic solution cold distilled water was added when milky white flakes appeared; the final m.p. 128-29°, yield 0.81 g. (or 40% of theory).

(ii). Heating in an oil-bath (105-110°) for 6 hours only slightly increased the yield (to 0.84 g., 42%). Its properties and reactions were the same as recorded for the *bis*-butyramide. (Found: N 7.9. Dihydrocinnamylidene-*bis*-*n*-heptamide, $C_{23}H_{38}O_4N_2$ requires N, 7.4 per cent).

Condensation with Formamide.—This did not seem to take place, although several different experiments were tried using various temperatures and heating periods, and using pyridine, alcohol, hydrochloric acid and no condensing reagent.

TABLE I

Amide.	Condensing agent.	Heating period.		Yield.
Formamide	Several & none	100° to 170° ; several hours		0
Acetamide	None	98-99°	9 hrs.	10.2%
"	Pyridine	"	11	9.35
"	None	120-125°	8	25.5
Propionamide	"	98-99°	8	11.8
"	Pyridine	"	11	9.6
"	None	110-120°	8	29
"	"	125-130°	8	12.1
n-Butyramide	"	98-99°	13	21.5
n-Heptamide	"	"	7	40
"	"	105-110°	8	42
Benzamide	"	98-99°	8	0
"	Pyridine	"	8	0
"	None	140-150°	2.5	40

TABLE II

Maximum yields from cinnamaldehyde and dihydrocinnamaldehyde.

Amide.	Cinnamaldehyde.	Dihydrocinnamaldehyde.
1. Formamide	A polyper ; yield good	0
2. Acetamide	51%	25.5%
3. Propionamide	48	29
4. n-Butyramide	(Not done)	40
5. n-Heptamide	42%	42
6. Benzamide	55	40

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